

RESEARCH PROPOSAL APPROVAL FORM

The University of Lethbridge Research Proposal Approval Form (RPAF) is to be used for **ALL** external funding proposals submitted to Research Services for approval. **Applications submitted without the accompanying RPAF WILL NOT be signed by Research Services and will be returned to the applicant.**

The completed RPAF will not be forwarded to the external funding agency, but will be kept on file in Research Services, along with a copy of your application.

The RPAF must be signed (in the following order) by:

1. the Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator(s)
2. the Department Chair
3. the Faculty Dean
4. the Vice-President (Research) or his representative

Signatures of the Department Chair and Dean must be on the RPAF and the application, before submission to Research Services. Research Services will obtain the remaining signatures, as required.

What do the signatures required on the Research Proposal Approval Form indicate?

Principal Investigator and Co-Investigator(s)

The signature of the principal investigator and co-investigator(s) indicates acceptance of academic, professional, scientific and technical responsibility for the project. In addition, it represents an undertaking to observe sponsor and University policies and regulations, as well as any special award conditions.

Department Chair and Dean

The signature of the Department Chair and Dean indicates that the Department is willing to accommodate the project, that required facilities and services are available, that funding is available for any required renovations, and that the applicant meets known University and sponsor eligibility requirements. It also represents general acceptance of expressed or implied time commitments, including willingness to recommend leave or other special arrangements as specified in the application.

Vice-President (Research) and Vice-President (Academic)

The signature of the Vice-President (Research) and the Vice-President (Academic) indicates that the University is willing to administer funds received for the project in accordance with University and funding agency regulations.

Vice-President (Finance & Administration)

The signature of the Vice-President (Finance & Administration) confirms that space required for the project is available.

Applications received two weeks prior to the application deadline, and containing the required signatures of approval, will be reviewed, signed, returned to the applicant for copying, and forwarded to the funding agency by Research Services. Applications received after this time will be reviewed, signed and returned to the applicant for copying and for submission to the funding agency.

Please contact Research Services regarding Animal Welfare, Human Subject Research, Radiation Safety or Biosafety Committee approval, if the project involves animals, human subjects, radioisotopes or biohazards. The principal investigator is responsible for ensuring that appropriate approval is obtained **in advance** of research being done.

Please call Research Services as early as possible during the application process, if you have any questions.

Research Proposal Approval Form

SECTION A – IDENTIFICATION

Principal Investigator		For Research Services use only:	
Name: O'Donnell, Daniel Paul		Application number:	
Academic unit: English		Submission deadline:	
Phone number: -2377		Date submitted:	
Co-Investigators (attach an additional sheet if necessary)		Application status:	
1.	see attached additional sheet	Amount awarded:	
2.		Account number:	
3.		Agency number:	

SECTION B – PROJECT

Project title: The Digital Medievalist Project: A Community of Practice Network for Image, Text, Sound and Technology Research		
Funding source: SSHRC	If this research is, or might be funded by other sources, specify:	
Proposed start date: 4/30/05	Proposed end date: 4/30/06	
Type of funding requested	This request is for:	Does this research require approval by the:
<div style="background-color: #ffff00; padding: 2px;">Research Grant</div> Equipment Grant Fellowship Conference Other Specify:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New funding <input type="checkbox"/> Continued funding	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal Welfare Committee <input type="checkbox"/> Radiation Safety Committee <input type="checkbox"/> Human Subject Research Committee <input type="checkbox"/> Biosafety Committee

SECTION C – RESEARCH BUDGET

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Total
Amount Requested	\$27,490.00					\$27,490.00
Overhead						\$0.00
University Contribution						\$0.00

Availability of University contribution confirmed by Dean:

_____	_____
Signature	Date

SECTION D – RESEARCH LOCATION

<i>Identify locations (rooms) that will be assigned to this research. Include all space required to accommodate research, research associates and equipment.</i>	
Research space(s): None	
Office(s) for researchers: TH 320	
Other space required to support this research:	
Date required:	
Renovations required? If so, please specify (additional pages may be attached if necessary): None	
Renovation cost estimate:	Confirmed by Director, Physical Plant:
Funding source:	Space availability and renovation funding confirmed by Dean:

SECTION E – REQUIRED SIGNATURES

For **Principal Investigators** and **Co-Investigators**: Your signature below means that "in consideration of the University signing the attached grant / contract to benefit your research, you agree to be bound by all the terms and conditions of the sponsoring agency."

Please check the box beside your signature to indicate that you have read this statement and agree to be bound by it.

[Redacted Signature]

Co-Investigator Date

Co-Investigator Date

Co-Investigator Date

The signatures of the **Department Chair** and **Dean** indicate their approval for the application. The Department is willing to accommodate the project, that required facilities and services are available, and that the applicant meets known University and sponsor eligibility requirements.

[Redacted Signature]

Department Chair Date

[Redacted Signature]

Vice-President (Research) Date

[Redacted Signature]

University of Cambridge representative
(in absence of Assoc. VP, Research) Date

Additional Co-Investigators

Baker, Peter. University of Virginia.

Cummings, James. University of Oxford.

Foys, Martin. Hood College.

McGillivray, Murray. University of Calgary.

Rosselli del Turco, Roberto. Università di Torino.

Solopova, Elizabeth. Bodleian Library, Oxford.

Image, Text, Sound and Technology Networking Grants

Internal use

Identification		
This page will be made available to selection committee members and external assessors.		
Program name Image, Text, Sound and Technology		
Grant type (Strategic Grants only) Networking Grant		
Application title The Digital Medievalist Project: A Community of Practice for Image, Text, Sound and Technology Research		
Applicant family name O'Donnell	Applicant given name Daniel	Initials P.
Org. code (Table 2) 1480411	Full name of administrative organization The University of Lethbridge	
Department/Division name Department of English		
Does your proposal involve human beings as research subjects? If "Yes", consult the <i>Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Human Subjects</i> and submit your proposal to your organization's Research Ethics Board. Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input checked="" type="radio"/>		
Total funds requested from SSHRC (from Page 6)		Total <u>27,490</u>

Signatures		
The undersigned accept the terms and conditions as outlined in the corresponding program description; the instructions provided with this form; and any conditions applied to a grant pursuant to this application.		
Applicant name (print) Daniel O'Donnell	Signature	Date
For department, institute, school		
Name (print) Chris Nicol	Signature	Date
For university		
Name (print) Dennis Fitzpatrick	Signature	Date

Social Sciences and Humanities
Research Council of Canada

Conseil de recherches en
sciences humaines du Canada

Family name, Given name
O'Donnell, Daniel

Co-applicants' and Institutional Signatures

I have read and agree to the requirements set out in the "Signatures" section of the accompanying instructions.

Signature, Name and Organization of Co-applicant	Signature and Name of Authorized Delegate for Organization

Social Sciences and Humanities
Research Council of Canada

Conseil de recherches en
sciences humaines du Canada

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Co-applicants' and Institutional Signatures

I have read and agree to the requirements set out in the "Signatures" section of the accompanying Instructions.

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Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Participants

List names of your research team members (co-applicants and collaborators) who will take part in the intellectual direction of the research. Do not include assistants, students or consultants.

Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)	
Family name Solopova		Given name Elizabeth	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name Bodleian Library Oxford, OX1 3BG United Kingdom		
Department/Division name Department of Special Collections and Western Manuscripts			
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)	
Family name Foy		Given name Martin	Initials K.
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name Hood College, Frederick MD 21701, USA		
Department/Division name Department of English			
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)	
Family name Rosselli del Turco		Given name Roberto	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name Università di Torino, Via S. Ottavio 20, 10126 Torino, Italy		
Department/Division name Dipartimento di Scienze del Linguaggio Letterature Moderne e Comparate			
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)	
Family name McGillivray		Given name Murray	Initials
Org. code (Table 2) 1480211	Full organization name The University of Calgary		
Department/Division name Department of English			
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)	
Family name Cummings		Given name James	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name The University of Oxford, Oxford, UK		
Department/Division name Oxford Text Archive			

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Participants (cont'd)		
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)
Family name Baker	Given name Peter	Initials S.
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name The University of Virginia, Charlottesville VI, 22903, USA	
Department/Division name Department of English		
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)
Family name	Given name	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name	
Department/Division name		
Role Co-applicant <input checked="" type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)
Family name	Given name	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name	
Department/Division name		
Role Co-applicant <input type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)
Family name	Given name	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name	
Department/Division name		
Role Co-applicant <input type="radio"/> Collaborator <input type="radio"/>		CID (if known)
Family name	Given name	Initials
Org. code (Table 2)	Full organization name	
Department/Division name		

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Research Activity

The information provided in this section refers to your research proposal.

Keywords

List keywords that best describe your proposed research or research activity. Separate keywords with a semicolon.

Image, Text, Sound, and Technology; Collaborative Networks; Best Practice; Communities of Practice; Information Technology; Humanities Computing; Medieval Studies

Disciplines

Indicate and rank up to 5 disciplines that best correspond to your proposal. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code (Table 3)	Discipline	If Other, specify
1	5606	Communications Technology, Informatics	
2	61208	Computer Assisted Instruction and Learning	
3	62624	Organizational Behaviour	
4	53099	Other Medieval Studies	Computer Applications
5			

Areas of Research

Indicate and rank up to 3 areas of research related to your proposal. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code (Table 4)	Area
1	242	Information Technologies
2	342	Post-Secondary Education and Research
3	100	Arts and Culture

Temporal Periods

If applicable, indicate up to 2 historical periods covered by your proposal.

From	To
<p>Year</p> <p>500</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>BC AD</p> <p><input type="radio"/> <input checked="" type="radio"/></p> <p><input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/></p>	<p>Year</p> <p>1500</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>BC AD</p> <p><input type="radio"/> <input checked="" type="radio"/></p> <p><input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/></p>

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Research Activity (cont'd)

Geographical Regions

If applicable, indicate and rank up to 3 geographical regions covered by or related to your proposal. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code (Table 5)	Region
1		
2		
3		

Countries

If applicable, indicate and rank up to 5 countries covered by or related to your proposal. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code (Table 6)	Country	Prov./ State
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Funds Requested from SSHRC

Estimate as accurately as possible the research costs that you are asking SSHRC to fund through a grant. For each category provided, enter the number of students and non-students to be hired, and specify the total amount required. Enter amounts rounded up to the nearest dollar without any spaces or commas.

Personnel costs

Student salaries and benefits	No.	Amount (\$)
Undergraduate	4	6,000
Masters		
Doctoral		

Non-student salaries and benefits

Postdoctoral		
Other	1	3,796

Travel and subsistence costs

Applicant

Canadian travel		3,846
Foreign travel		9,092

Students

Canadian travel		847
Foreign travel		1,177

Other expenses

Professional/technical expenses		
Supplies		
Non-disposable equipment		
Computer hardware		
Other		

Other expenses (specify)

Network Association Fees		2,732
Total funds requested from SSHRC		27,490

Communication of research results

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Funds from Other Sources

You must include all other sources of funding for the proposed research. Indicate whether these funds have been confirmed or not. Where applicable, include a) the partners' material contributions (e.g., cash and in-kind), and b) funds you have requested from other sources for proposed research related to this application. Enter amounts rounded up to the nearest dollar without any spaces or commas.

Full organization name	Contribution type (Table 11)	Confirmed	Amount (\$)
University of Lethbridge	Research Time Stipend	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	25,000
University of Lethbridge	in-kind	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2,600
		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Total funds from other sources			27,600

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell Daniel

Funds from Other Sources (cont'd)			
Full organization name	Contribution type (Table 11)	Confirmed	Amount (\$)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Total funds from other sources			27,600

A Summary of Proposed Research

This application is to fund the networking activities of the Digital Medievalist Project, an international network of over 200 medieval scholars and students whose research and teaching projects use Image, Text, Sound, and Technology (ITST). The project is hosted at the University of Lethbridge and moderated by an international executive of seven medievalists with significant ITST experience.

The Digital Medievalist Project was established in 2003 in order to improve the networking ability of medievalist ITST researchers. Recent ITST projects show great technical accomplishment due in part to training initiatives by agencies such as SSHRC. Developing consistent and predictable implementations of international technical standards is the next major challenge facing the field, however. Although well-developed international standards and languages exist for most aspects of contemporary ITST research, projects vary greatly in both the rigour with which they follow the published standards and the specific approach they take to their interpretation. This problem is significant because it prevents humanities computing projects from easily exchanging and reusing complex data, and because the duplication of effort it implies can represent a significant drain on such projects' usually small budgets. Evidence suggests that this problem is not caused by the lack of technical expertise among researchers. Rather, it is caused by the lack of an easy and effective means of discovering and sharing how others are doing the same thing—in other words, of networking.

The Digital Medievalist addresses this problem using the Community of Practice networking model. Communities of Practice are self-organising disciplinary networks whose members are bound together by a common interest in improving their knowledge and skill in the practice of a given area of expertise. Research has demonstrated that this networking model is particularly successful in fields that require practitioners to master intellectually challenging, rapidly changing, and highly abstract or codified systems or processes. In such fields Communities of Practice become nodes for the exchange and interpretation of information; repositories of 'living' knowledge that formal systems cannot capture; centers for competence and identity.

In practical terms, the Digital Medievalist Project encourages this networking through four main types of activities. Using a central Community of Practice portal designed and hosted at the University of Lethbridge, the project operates a moderated mailing list, refereed on-line journal, and wiki-based collaborative knowledgebase. The project also sponsors sessions on ITST research at the major disciplinary conferences (Kalamazoo 2004-; Leeds 2006-) and participates in activities at significant Humanities computing events, include SSHRC funded ITST workshops, and meetings of major ITST organisations.

By sponsoring these networking activities, the Digital Medievalist Project helps medievalists refine their ability to apply digital multimedia technologies in three main ways:

- It encourages the collaborative development of dissemination of discipline-specific best practice
- It provides a network through which ITST researchers can collaborate to improve their technological skills, follow new technological developments, and discover other researchers tackling similar problems in their own work
- It eases entry into ITST research for novice researchers by encouraging collaboration with more experienced researchers in a discipline-specific setting.

The project is rapidly becoming acknowledged as the principal networking agent in the discipline: several collaborative research projects have already had their start through the networking activities of the project (e.g. Foys, Karkov, and O'Donnell 2004-; O'Donnell, Porter, and Rosselli del Turco 2004-; Foys and Westrem 2004-), and, beginning in 2006, the project will play a major role in coordinating IT conference sessions at major disciplinary conferences. The project was a prize winner at the recent 2004 Digital Resources in the Humanities conference in Sheffield.

B Detailed Project Description

1 Objective

This application is for support to fund the networking activities of the **Digital Medievalist Project**.

Founded in 2003, the Digital Medievalist Project is an international network of over 200 scholars whose research and teaching projects use Image, Text, Sound, and Technology (ITST). Based on the Community of Practice networking model, the project helps its members refine their ability to apply digital multimedia technologies to their ITST research and teaching activities in three ways:

1. It encourages the collaborative development and dissemination of disciplinary best-practice in the application of technology to research and teaching problems involving images, text, and, where applicable, sound
2. It provides a means through which ITST researchers can cooperate in improving their technological skills, share information about new developments in multimedia technology and theory, and discover and address common research problems
3. It eases entry for medievalists into ITST research by encouraging collaboration between novice and experienced ITST researchers in the development of disciplinary technological primers, guides to best practice, and tutorials.

The project accomplishes these goals through four main types of activities:

1. A moderated electronic mailing list, <dm-l@uleth.ca>, devoted to the free discussion of all aspects of the application of ITS technology to problems in the study of medieval culture
2. A refereed on-line journal, *DM* <<http://www.digitalmedievalist.org/journal.dfm>>, to provide a quality forum for the sharing of formal ITST research results
3. A network wiki (collaborative reference site) <<http://www.digitalmedievalist.org/wiki/index.dfm>> through which members collaborate in the development of primers, FAQ files, and accounts of disciplinary best practice
4. Conference sessions and functions at the major international medievalist congresses (with proceedings published in revised and refereed forum in subsequent issues of *DM*) where members meet, discuss research results, and discover common problems in a disciplinary setting.

The virtual aspects of the Digital Medievalist Project are accessed through a central internet portal hosted and designed at the University of Lethbridge <<http://www.digitalmedievalist.org/>>. The network is directed by O'Donnell (Lethbridge) and overseen by an executive of seven medievalists with significant experience in different aspects of ITST research: Baker (Virginia), Cummings (Oxford Text Archive), Foys (Hood College), McGillivray (Calgary), O'Donnell, Rosselli del Turco (Torino), and Solopova (Bodleian Library). Graduate student apprentices at the co-applicants universities play significant roles in several of the project's networking activities. Additional expert support and interdisciplinary advice is provided through a network of formal and informal collaborators and advisors.

2 The Problem

The Digital Medievalist network was established in 2003 to address the problem of inconsistent implementation of ITST standards in scholarly multimedia projects (see HATII and NINCH 2002, NINCH 2002-2003, Healey 2003, O'Donnell 2003). Although well-developed international standards and languages exist for almost all aspects of contemporary ITST research, these standards have proved difficult to implement consistently and predictably across independent projects. Although it is

increasingly rare, potentially significant ITST projects still are proposed and implemented using non-standard markup, character encoding, image formats and production standards. Projects that are standards-based, moreover, frequently vary greatly in both the rigour with which they follow these standards and the specific approach they take to their interpretation. Image standards, formats and integration, markup style, and transcription methods and standards vary greatly and unpredictably. User interfaces rarely if ever share the same layout or organisation, even in projects issued by the same press. Common elements of digital editions—the representation of alternative readings, or the representation of additions, deletions and emendations—are frequently encoded using incompatible though legal interpretations of common standards.

This problem is significant for two reasons. In the first place, inconsistent interpretation and implementation of published standards prevents projects from fully realising one of the most significant theoretical benefits of standards-based computing: the ability to exchange, reuse and repurpose complex data in response to developing research or technological imperatives (NINCH 1999 and, concentrating on the needs of a different community, Simons and Bird 2003). While standards such as the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) *Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange* (Sperberg-McQueen and Burnard 2002) or the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) Extensible Hypertext Markup Language (XHTML) (W3C 2002) offer powerful tools for standards-based ITST research, their necessarily abstract and highly codified nature allows considerable scope for variation in implementation by individual users. This in turn prevents the easy reuse of previously encoded data. Data encoded by one project often cannot be incorporated into another without the use of customized conversion routines, even when such projects make use of a common standard language. Changes required to update obsolete projects in response to technological innovation similarly often must be discovered and implemented on a case-by-case basis—when indeed, they prove at all possible (see Simons and Bird 2003). Potential future applications based on access to large amounts of independently encoded data—a variorum corpus of Old or Middle English prose based on previously published electronic editions, for example—would be difficult to realise economically due to current encoding incompatibilities among otherwise comparable projects. Although the increasing adherence to published standards by individual projects is a promising development, the failure of these projects to implement such standards in a common and predictable fashion hinders future reuse and repurposing.

Inconsistency in the interpretation and implementation of published ITST standards is also significant because it is symptomatic of a deeper problem: unnecessary duplication (and hence waste) of effort by ITST researchers (O'Donnell 2003). While some variation in implementation is no doubt to be attributed to deliberate intellectual disagreement, other differences among projects appear to be little more than the result of independent attempts at solving common problems in isolation. Differences in basic elements of user interface seem almost certainly to be the result of duplicated effort: in contrast to commercial software design where convergence in user interface is the norm, few if any scholarly ITST projects share common standards of layout or operation or show any movement in this direction. Similar problems can exist in the implementation of more fundamental standards: a recent discussion on the TEI mailing list concerning the encoding of large textual structures such as numbered and unnumbered divisions, for example, suggested that significant yet unnecessary variation in encoding practice among projects has arisen through a failure on the part of the community to preserve a record of the preferred interpretation of their common encoding standard (TEI 2003, esp. messages 005134-37, 005139-40, 005149 and associated replies).

In many cases, such duplication of effort leads to the development of comparable but incompatible solutions to shared problems—and hence a direct threat to the major theoretical advantage of standards-based ITST. Even when such independent solutions are not ultimately incompatible, however, the waste this unnecessary duplication involves can impose a significant drain on the small staffs and low budgets

typical of most humanities research projects. Indeed, anecdotal evidence suggests that some medievalists have abandoned (or reverted to non-standards based technologies to complete) otherwise promising projects due to the perceived difficulty involved in implementing standards-based ITST projects.

3 A Model Solution: The Community of Practice Network

The inconsistency of interpretation and implementation of published ITST standards discussed above is in our view more a failure of networking and collaboration than basic training. Most recently completed ITST projects show a generally high degree of technical accomplishment. ITST training, due in part to SSHRC funded summer institutes, workshops and conferences, is increasingly available to novice and experienced ITST researchers alike. Comparable problems of compatibility, moreover, arise among large projects that have trained technical staff and well-developed internal guidelines. Indeed the willingness of ITST projects to solve complex problems independently is itself evidence of the strong skills of their staff. The problem is not that ITST researchers do not understand how to interpret the published standards; it is that they lack an easy and effective means of networking in order to discover and collaborate with others doing the same thing.

It is in this context, then, that the Digital Medievalist Project has adopted the “Community of Practice” model for the collaborative creation, accumulation and dissemination of communal knowledge and resources (see Brown and Duguid 1991 for an early description; discussion of how this model can be applied to virtual communities can be found in Sharp 1997, Wenger 1998, and Deloitte Research 2001).

The “Community of Practice” is, in its purest form, a ubiquitous type of self-organising social group whose members are bound together by a common interest in improving their knowledge and skill in the practice of a given area of expertise. While research has demonstrated that such communities form spontaneously among practitioners in any field of human activity—from members of a church choir (Wenger 1998), to perhaps most famously, Xerox service technicians (Brown and Duguid 1991; Deloitte Research 2001)—the learning model has proven particularly successful in fields that require practitioners to master intellectually challenging, rapidly changing, and highly abstract or codified systems or processes (Sharp 1997; Wenger 1998; Deloitte Research 2001). In such fields, according to Wenger, Communities of Practice fulfill at least four functions that make them particularly well suited as a solution to the problem identified above and a network funded under the SSHRC ITST networking program:

1. They are nodes for the *exchange and interpretation of information*. Because members have a shared understanding, they know what is relevant to communicate and how to present information in useful ways. As a consequence, a community of practice that spreads... is an ideal channel for moving information, such as best practices, tips or feedback, across organizational boundaries.
2. They can *retain knowledge* in “living” ways, unlike a database or a manual. Even when they routinize certain tasks and processes, they can do so in a manner that responds to local circumstances and thus is useful to practitioners. Communities of practice preserve the tacit aspects of knowledge that formal systems cannot capture. For this reason, they are ideal for initiating newcomers into a practice.
3. They can *steward competencies* to keep the organization at the cutting edge. Members of these groups discuss novel ideas, work together on problems and keep up with developments inside and outside... [an organisation]. When a community commits to being on the forefront of a field, members distribute responsibility for keeping up with or pushing new developments. This collaborative inquiry makes membership valuable, because people invest their professional identities in being part of a dynamic, forward-looking community.
4. They provide *homes for identities*. They are not as temporary as teams and unlike business units, they are organized around what matters to their members. Identity is important because, in a sea of

information, it helps us sort out what we pay attention to, what we participate in and what we stay away from. Having a sense of identity is a crucial aspect of learning in organizations.

(Wenger 1998; emphasis as in original)

4 Current Implementation

Although the Community of Practice networking model has proven itself to be extremely effective in the creation, accumulation and dissemination of knowledge and practice, such communities are notorious for being easier to nurture than create (Sharp 1997, Wenger 1998, Deloitte Research 2001). Communities of Practice develop most easily when they arise from already-existing alliances among practitioners and are provided with an appropriate collaborative infrastructure. Accordingly, the Digital Medievalist network has restricted itself in scope to scholars belonging to a well defined, highly organised, and computer literate research community, and in format to the development of networking events and a collaborative infrastructure that allows this already existing disciplinary network to thrive. By organising (virtual and physical) networking events and activities at which medievalists active in ITST can meet and discuss common problems and solutions, the Digital Medievalist Project helps the discipline as a whole refine its use of digital multimedia technologies to their research on image, text, and sound.

5 Current networking activity

As a Community of Practice network, the Digital Medievalist Project creates opportunities for ITST researchers to interact with and learn from their peers. As mentioned above (§ 1), this is done in four main ways: through an on-line discussion list, a refereed journal, a community wiki, and conference sessions organised at the most important medievalist congresses.

5.1 Discussion list

The discussion list provides a wide-ranging forum for the collaborative exchange of ideas and information concerning all aspects of ITST by scholars engaged in the digital representation of medieval material. Under this mandate, <dm-l@uleth.ca> occupies a place not directly covered by any comparable tool or organisation: it is less tied to a specific language, application or type of activity than lists such as *tei-l* or *sedit-l*; it is more open to detailed discussion of detailed technical and design problems than theoretical lists such as *humanist-l* or lists devoted more generally to research into the culture of a specific period, genre or theoretical approach (e.g. *medtext-l*, *ansax-l* or *sharp-l*); it is more focussed on the specific needs of scholars engaged in ITST research than general lists such as *xsl-l*.

5.2 Refereed journal

The refereed journal (inaugural issue, fall 2004) publishes original work on technical, procedural and design issues in ITST. The goal of this journal is to provide a formal mechanism to help eliminate duplication of effort in scholarly ITST production. It encourages ITST scholars to share solutions to technical, procedural and design problems by allowing them to claim authorship of significant developments and by rewarding their efforts with refereed publication (see Wenger 1998 and Deloitte Research 2001 for the importance of reward systems in “nurturing” Communities of Practice). In addition to original research, the journal also publishes project reports (in which authors describe significant features of on-going research), technical notes, and commentary pieces (in which authors discuss contemporary developments in ITST research in a more pedagogical—or polemical—fashion).

5.3 Wiki

The Digital Medievalist wiki is used for two major complementary tasks:

1. establishing, disseminating, revising, and reflecting on community consensus concerning technological and theoretical developments and best practice in medievalist ITST research;

2. helping medievalists refine their ability to apply digital multimedia technologies to their ITS research by publishing articles on essential knowledge and skills (e.g. definitions of important acronyms; discussions and lists of resources for learning basic skills, concepts, and languages).

Articles in the Digital Medievalist wiki are written, edited, and maintained by members of the project community, or captured from on-line discussion in the project mailing list. The project wiki differs from more general-interest examples (e.g. the Wikipedia), however, in that a stronger editorial control is exerted: in keeping with the peer-reviewed nature of the project, anonymous contributions are discouraged, and contributions are restricted to discussion of issues affect the scholarly use of ITST. In the future, the Project hopes to commission its members to collaborate on wiki-based “books” and primers on specific subjects (e.g. beginning a new project; small project management, etc.) as networking activities designed to capture the collective knowledge of the network.

5.4 Conference Sessions

As a Community of Practice for Medievalists engaged in ITST research, the Digital Medievalist Project must remained integrated into the larger research communities. In order to make researchers aware of technological developments, and encourage them to participate in their integration in contemporary medieval research, the Project hosts conference sessions and holds its annual meeting at the significant annual international Medieval Congresses in Kalamazoo (2004-) and (assuming appropriate future funding), Leeds (2006-) (e.g. O'Donnell 2003; Baker *et al.* 2004a-b). Equally important is the organisation's participation in major national and international humanities computing conferences and organisations: the COCH annual meeting at the Congress of the Humanities and Social Sciences (Canada), the Digital Resources in the Humanities Conference (UK), and the TEI annual meeting (e.g. Baker *et al.* 2004c; O'Donnell 2004a-c).

This physical networking activity represents the largest continuing cost of the project. The importance of providing a disciplinary forum in which ITST researchers can meet face to face cannot be underestimated. The idea of the project as a whole was launched from discussions at the 2003 Kalamazoo conference; one member of the project executive—and most members of the larger community—joined the project after hearing about it at the 2004 conference. Several new projects have had their beginning at sessions sponsored by the Digital Medievalist Project (e.g. Foys, Karkov, and O'Donnell 2004-; O'Donnell, Porter, and Rosselli del Turco 2004-; Foys and Westrem 2004-). By sponsoring sessions and publishing research presented at major medievalist conferences, the Digital Medievalist Project encourages researchers to meet each other, interact, and forge alliances that can then be further developed on-line using the project's other tools.

6 Significance of proposal

In our unsuccessful 2003 ITST application, the committee noted that our “topic was an interesting one and that the participants were well qualified,” but went on to suggest

that there was no clear explanation regarding the networking of the participants or how anticipated networking fitted with the objectives of the ITST program... [and] that the budget was not justified in terms of the networking activities of the participants but rather in terms of administrative, technical and conference costs [see attachments for a copy of the full text].

We believe we have been able to improve our project (and application for funding) in light of these comments in the following ways:

1. Because our networking infrastructure is now largely in place, we are able in this application to concentrate on the project's networking activities.
2. In the course of the last year, we have been able to establish a short but significant track record in

disciplinary networking activities. This track record includes our already large (200+ members) and active mailing list, successful conference sessions, and invited participation at a number of other ITST conferences, workshops, and networking activities, including several funded through the 2003 SSHRC ITST programs and our prize winning poster at the 2004 DRH conference (Baker *et al.* 2004a-c; O'Donnell 2004a-c).

Indeed, the Digital Medievalist is already yielding significant results for users in both in its target audience and the larger world of ITST research. As a collaboration based on the demonstrably successful Community of Practice networking model, the Digital Medieval Project allows researchers to leverage work by other ITST training and infrastructure initiatives. Individuals, groups and projects working on discipline- or project-specific guidelines are using our network to share their results; developers of ITST tools for projects such as the CFI funded TAPoR project (TAPOR nd), Peter Robinson's Anastasia and Collate software (Scholarly Digital Editions 2003) or Kevin Kiernan's Digital Atheneum Project have used our network to publicise the encoding decisions their tools imply, more easily acquire information on the current practice of active ITST scholars and improve the interoperability and standardisation of tools produced by different projects. The project executive has been invited to give lectures and present posters on its networking model at several conference since its inception, including SSHRC-funded ITST workshops from the 2003 competition (Baker *et al.* 2004c; O'Donnell 2004a-c). Its membership grew to 200 within two months of its launch. As a network aimed at developing and refining the ability of medievalists to apply digital multimedia technologies to their research on image, text, and sound, the project appears to be more than meeting its original goals.

7 Research Training Opportunities for Students

The Digital Medievalist Project is intended as a network for the benefit of ITST researchers, a community in which graduate and undergraduate students are very active (examples include Bernstein 1996; Rambaran-Olm 2002). One member of the journal's editorial board, Kenna Olsen, is a PhD candidate at the University of Calgary; several speakers at the project's 2003 sessions were graduate students in North America or Europe. The participation in <dm-l@digitalmedievalist.org> of students working for degree credit on Medieval ITST projects will be actively encouraged. More concretely, the project budget envisages the direct participation of students working under the supervision of O'Donnell, and the CRDC (the University of Lethbridge's IT development office), on improving the project's collaborative software. A second more informal element of training will occur in the applicants' home institutions: as part of their normal supervisory duties, the applicants expect to have students actively engaged in ITST resource discovery: reviewing practice at other ITST projects and preparing reports on current standards. This material will then be used by the applicants and their students to begin an example-based guide to best practice and prepare material on current disciplinary ITST standards for refereed publication.

8 Conclusion

The Digital Medievalist Project is a disciplinary ITST networking program. Its goal is to encourage the interaction of its already large membership—in person and electronically—in order to accomplish the principal objectives of the ITST program: reflect on, interpret, and analyse new digital technology and integrate these into humanities and social science research; bring together researchers from different disciplines to share and nurture new ideas and methods for using new technology in disciplinary research; and facilitate the creation of national and international networks and partnerships that will promote and sustain social sciences and humanities research and resources. It does this through a variety of virtual and physical events. The project (and its model) is already having an effect on the use of ITST in medieval studies.

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D Description of Team

The Digital Medievalist team consists of seven medievalists with significant experience in ITST and two collaborators with strong profiles in user modelling and information technology management.

- **Baker, Peter.** Professor of English, University of Virginia. Baker has edited two Old English and two early modern texts. He is the author of a multimedia introductory Old English textbook and several other digital pedagogical tools. His Junicode font is widely used by medievalists for the display of specialized characters. Baker is network moderator for discussion of edition design and usability issues on the network.
- **Cummings, James.** Research Officer, Oxford Text Archive, University of Oxford. Cummings worked on the UK's AHRB-funded *CURSUS* project (medieval liturgical documents) and is editing an electronic edition of *The Conversion of St Paul*. As a representative for the AHDS, he advises funding applicants on ITST best practice. Cummings moderates network discussion of markup issues, especially XML and XSL implementations.
- **Foys, Martin.** Assistant Professor of English, Hood College, MD. Foys edited the *Digital Bayeux Tapestry* and is involved in other projects involving the representation of physical artifacts. He has professional experience in multimedia design and production. Foys moderates network discussion of the representation of physical artifacts and the integration of text and images.
- **McGillivray, Murray.** Professor (formerly Head) of English, University of Calgary. McGillivray has published three electronic editions, including the SSHRC-funded *Book of the Duchess*; he is at work on a fourth. He co-authored a report on scholarly electronic publishing for the HSSF. He moderates network discussion of HTML encoding issues in the project.
- **O'Donnell, Daniel Paul.** Associate Professor of English, University of Lethbridge. O'Donnell edited the *Electronic Cædmon's Hymn* (forthcoming spring 2005) and is at work on several other electronic projects. He lectures on computer applications in the humanities. He is the team leader and moderates network discussion on structural encoding, project management and edition design.
- **Rosselli Del Turco, Roberto.** Ricercatore, Linguistics and Comparative Literature, University of Turin. Rosselli Del Turco is director of the *Digital Vercelli Book Project* and has recently published a study, edition and translation of the *Battle of Maldon*. Rosselli Del Turco moderates network discussion on ITST project management, structural encoding, and image-based editing in this project.
- **Solopova, Elizabeth.** Project Manager, Electronic Catalogue of Medieval and Renaissance Manuscripts, Bodleian Library. Solopova edited the *General Prologue to the Canterbury Tales* and contributed to the *Electronic Beowulf*. She has served as support officer for OxTALENT and led numerous ITST training seminars. She is especially responsible for moderating network discussion of text analysis issues.

E Training and/or Role of Student Research Assistants

The Digital Medievalist Project anticipates paid training opportunities for at least 4 undergraduate research assistants. All four will be hired to work on maintaining and improving the Digital Medievalist Project's ability to promote collaboration and networking on the virtual side of its activities. These students will work under the supervision of O'Donnell, and the director of the University of Lethbridge IT development office (CRDC), Trevor J. Woods. Additional supervision may be provided by colleagues from the students' home departments or faculties.

The precise nature of student participation in the project depends on the program requirements and interests of students accepted into the project. Based on past experience at the CRDC and with research assistants employed by O'Donnell on earlier projects, we anticipate interest from students in the Faculties of Arts and Science, Fine Arts (Multimedia), and Management (Information Technology). The project would be particularly suited to students pursuing degrees in Multimedia, Management ITS, Math and Computer Science, or to humanities students working on honours theses with a significant ITST component. While graduate student participation is possible, it is not currently anticipated: we are aware of no suitable students currently enrolled in the University of Lethbridge's graduate school—a program that is only now entering its fourth year.

Undergraduate students hired as research assistants will receive a stipend of \$1,500 per semester. Should Graduate student assistants become available, their precise duties and remuneration will be arranged in accordance with the policies of the Graduate school in cooperation with the Dean of the Graduate School and the student's program director.

F Budget Justification

The Digital Medievalist Project is requesting funding for its networking activities. As a disciplinary organisation with over 200 members, this networking takes place in virtual and physical forms. We operate a mailing list, collaborative reference web-site (wiki), on-line journal and resource centre, and organise sessions and other networking activities at major disciplinary conferences. In the course of the last year, the project has become a significant agent for networking among ITST researchers in medieval studies internationally. The two major costs of this networking activity are travel (to enable the executive to attend the major disciplinary meeting for physical networking) and student salaries (to maintain and improve the Community of Practice software which allows for the project's virtual networking activities). Membership in Ninch and the TEI—two significant member-driven ITST networks in their own right—is a third cost.

1 Student salaries and benefits (\$6,000)

We anticipate spending \$6,000 on stipends for four semester-long undergraduate internships and co-op placements (\$1500 per student). Students from the Faculties of Arts and Science, Fine Arts (Multimedia), and Management (Information Technology) at the University of Lethbridge will be eligible for these positions, which will involve maintaining and improving the Digital Medievalist Project's ability to promote collaboration and networking. The main focus of this employment will be improving the integration of the disparate elements of the relatively new website and general maintenance and data management.

2 Non-student salaries and benefits (\$3,796)

We anticipate spending \$3,796 on a networking coordinator/administrator (=8hrs/week @ \$14.00 + 13% benefits for 30 weeks). This person will be responsible for coordinating the project's day-to-day networking activities. The coordinator/administrator will serve as the executive's liaison with student assistants, professional and technical consultants. He or she will also administer details of the network's participation in scholarly conferences, and manage correspondence among the network executive, collaborators, and outside associations, projects, and organisations. While preference will be given to students in hiring for this position, the position itself is listed as "non-student" because it is less obviously associated with a specific program of study.

3 Travel and subsistence costs (\$14,962)

We anticipate spending \$14,962 on travel and subsistence costs for the principal, co-applicants, and PhD student Kenna Olsen. Participation in these conferences is the principal networking expense of the project. The figure is based on the costs involved in organising sessions and our annual meeting at the 40th International Congress on Medieval Studies in Kalamazoo (\$8,275), with additional participation from the principal, two co-applicants (McGillivray, Cummings), and student Olsen at the COCH sessions of the Canadian Congress of the Social Sciences and Humanities in May/June 2005 (\$4,693), and the participation of the principal at the 2005 Digital Resources in the Humanities Conference (UK, \$1,994). The principal also intends to attend the 2005 TEI meeting; as the location of this is still TBA, he will seek other funding for this travel.

As mentioned in our detailed description, this conference participation is the main physical networking activity of the project. It has also proven extraordinarily fruitful. Our sessions at the 2004 Kalamazoo conference were well attended, and our project membership jumped immediately afterwards. As importantly, our participation at the meeting served as a locus for medievalists interested in digital applications to meet each other and discover common interests and problems. The organiser of a different session at the 2005 meeting has recently suggested that the Digital Medievalist Project should perhaps serve a more formal coordinating function from 2006 onwards. We are currently discussing the

possibility with other projects and session organisers.

Participation in these conferences is also significant because of the disciplinary focus of our networking activities. The Kalamazoo (and beginning in 2006) Leeds congresses are the most significant annual conferences for medievalists in North America and Europe respectively and both host a number of sessions on ITST research each year. By organising sessions, advertising calls for papers, and delivering lectures, we are able to organise our networking activities with the largest number of participants and—since most participants are already attending the Kalamazoo conference for disciplinary reasons—at the lowest possible cost. It is for this reason, indeed, that we are scheduling our business meeting to coincide with the Kalamazoo conference.

Our source for these estimates are based on the average airfare to the host city from the home cities of the relevant applicants as listed on expedia.ca on August 30th, 2004. Registration fees and subsistence costs are based on 2004 fees when available; otherwise, the 2003 fees have been used.

4 Other expenses [*Network Association Fees*] (\$2,732)

We anticipate spending \$2,732 on membership fees for major ITST Network Associations: \$685 to join the National Initiative for a Networked Cultural Heritage (NINCH) and \$2,055 to join the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI). Both organisations are important standards bodies and both are active in the development of best practice standards for humanities computing. Membership in both is important if members of the Digital Medievalist network are to have an influence on further developments in ITST; indeed the TEI has just initiated a Special Interest Group (SIG) program which appears to be of particular relevance for this project. In both cases, membership is restricted to projects rather than individuals.

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Internal use	CID (if known)
722447	57402

Identification				
Only the information in the Name section will be made available to selection committee members and external assessors. Citizenship and Statistical and Administrative Information will be used by SSHRC for administrative and statistical purposes only. Filling out the statistical and Administrative Information section is optional.				
Name				
Family name		Given name		Initials
O'Donnell		Daniel		P
				Title
				Dr.
Citizenship - Applicants and co-applicants must indicate their citizenship status by checking and answering the applicable questions.				
Citizenship status	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Canadian	<input type="radio"/> Permanent resident since (yyyy/mm/dd)	<input type="radio"/> Other (country)	Have you applied for permanent residency?
		____ / ____ / ____	_____	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
Statistical and Administrative Information				
Birth year	Gender	Permanent postal code in Canada (i.e. K2P1G4)	Correspondence language	Previous contact with SSHRC? (i.e. applicant, assessor, etc.)
1966	<input type="radio"/> F <input checked="" type="radio"/> M	T1J2X5	<input checked="" type="radio"/> English <input type="radio"/> French	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
Full name used during previous contact, if different from above				

Contact Information							
The following information will help us to contact you more rapidly. Secondary information will not be released by SSHRC without your express consent.							
Primary telephone number				Secondary telephone number			
Country code	Area code	Number	Extension	Country code	Area code	Number	Extension
1	403	381-2539		1	403	329-2377	
Primary fax number				Secondary fax number			
Country code	Area code	Number	Extension	Country code	Area code	Number	Extension
1	403	382-7191					
Primary E-mail daniel.odonnell@uleth.ca							
Secondary E-mail							

Signature	
I certify that the information provided is accurate and complete; that I have read and understood the references to the Access to Information and Privacy Acts, and that I consent to the uses and disclosures described.	
Signature	Date

Personal information will be stored in the Personal Information Bank for the appropriate program.

Checked

Web CV

2004/09/13

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Family name, Given name

O'Donnell, Daniel

Research Expertise (optional)

The information provided in this section refers to your own research expertise, not to a research proposal. Filling out the following 4 sections is optional. This page will not be seen by selection committee members and external assessors. This section will be used for planning and evaluating programs, producing statistics, and selecting external assessors and committee members.

Areas of Research

Indicate and rank up to 3 areas of research that best correspond to your research interests as well as areas where your research interests would apply. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code	Area
1	100	Arts and culture
2	280	Literacy
3		

Temporal Periods

If applicable, indicate up to 2 historical periods covered by your research interests.

From	To
<p style="text-align: center;">Year</p> <p style="text-align: center;">_____ 449 BC AD</p> <p style="text-align: center;">_____ <input type="radio"/> <input checked="" type="radio"/></p> <p style="text-align: center;">_____ <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Year</p> <p style="text-align: center;">_____ 1250 BC AD</p> <p style="text-align: center;">_____ <input type="radio"/> <input checked="" type="radio"/></p> <p style="text-align: center;">_____ <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/></p>

Geographical Regions

If applicable, indicate and rank up to 3 geographical regions covered by your research interests. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code	Region
1	3200	Western Europe
2		
3		

Countries

If applicable, indicate and rank up to 5 countries covered by your research interests. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code	Countries	Prov./ State
1	3225	UNITED KINGDOM	
2	3218	NETHERLANDS, THE	
3	3210	IRELAND/EIRE	
4	3206	GERMANY	
5	3105	NORWAY	

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell, Daniel

Curriculum Vitae

Language Proficiency

	Read	Write	Speak	Comprehend aurally	Other languages
English	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dutch, German, Irish Gaelic, Latin, early Germanic languages
French	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Work Experience

List the positions, academic and non-academic, you have held beginning with the current position and all previous positions in reverse chronological order, based on the start year.

Current position		Start year (yyyy)
Associate Professor		2002
Org. code	Full organization name	
1480411	The University of Lethbridge	
Department/Division name		
English		
Position type	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Tenured <input type="radio"/> Non-tenure <input type="radio"/> Tenure-track <input type="radio"/> Non-academic	Employment status
		<input checked="" type="radio"/> Full-time <input type="radio"/> Part-time <input type="radio"/> Leave of absence <input type="radio"/> Non-salaried <input type="radio"/> Retired
Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)
Assistant Professor	1997	2002
Org. code	Full organization name	
1480411	The University of Lethbridge	
Department/Division name		
English		
Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)
Tutor	1997	1997
Org. code	Full organization name	
1	Workers' Educational Association	
Department/division name		
N/A		
Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)
Tutor	1997	1997
Org. code	Full organization name	
9121150	University of York, UK	
Department/Division name		
English		

Personal information will be stored in the Personal Information Bank for the appropriate program.

Web CV

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell, Daniel

Work Experience (cont'd)

Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)
Visiting Professor	1994	1995

Org. code	Full organization name
9967102	Louisiana State University

Department/Division name
English

Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)
Teaching Assistant	1991	1992

Org. code	Full organization name
9929101	Yale University

Department/Division name
English

Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)
Research Assistant	1986	1989

Org. code	Full organization name
1350911	University of Toronto

Department/Division name
Dictionary of Old English

Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)

Org. code	Full organization name

Department/Division name

Position	Start year (yyyy)	End year (yyyy)

Org. code	Full organization name

Department/Division name

Academic Background				
List up to 5 degrees, beginning with the highest degree first and all others in reverse chronological order, based on the start date.				
Degree type	Degree name	Start date (yyyy/mm)	Expected date (yyyy/mm)	Awarded date (yyyy/mm)
Doctorate		1992/09	/	1996/05
Disc. code	Discipline	Did SSHRC support enable you to get this degree?		
52100	Literature, English	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No		
Org. code	Organization			
9929101	Yale University			
Country UNITED STATES				
Degree type	Degree name	Start date (yyyy/mm)	Expected date (yyyy/mm)	Awarded date (yyyy/mm)
Master's		1989/09	/	1991/05
Disc. code	Discipline	Did SSHRC support enable you to get this degree?		
52100	Literature, English	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No		
Org. code	Organization			
9929101	Yale University			
Country UNITED STATES				
Degree type	Degree name	Start date (yyyy/mm)	Expected date (yyyy/mm)	Awarded date (yyyy/mm)
BA Hon.		1985/09	/	1989/05
Disc. code	Discipline	Did SSHRC support enable you to get this degree?		
52100	Literature, English	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No		
Org. code	Organization			
1350911	University of Toronto			
Country CANADA				
Degree type	Degree name	Start date (yyyy/mm)	Expected date (yyyy/mm)	Awarded date (yyyy/mm)
		/	/	/
Disc. code	Discipline	Did SSHRC support enable you to get this degree?		
		<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No		
Org. code	Organization			
Country				
Degree type	Degree name	Start date (yyyy/mm)	Expected date (yyyy/mm)	Awarded date (yyyy/mm)
		/	/	/
Disc. code	Discipline	Did SSHRC support enable you to get this degree?		
		<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No		
Org. code	Organization			
Country				

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell, Daniel

Credentials

List up to 6 licences, professional designations, awards and distinctions you have received and feel would be the most pertinent to the adjudication of your application. List them in reverse chronological order, based on the year awarded.

Category	Name	Country	Year awarded (yyyy)
Fellowship	SSHRC Doctoral Fellowship		1991
Fellowship	Mellon Fellowship in the Humanities	UNITED STATES	1989
Fellowship	Yale University Graduate Fellowship	UNITED STATES	1989

Research Expertise

The information provided in this section refers to your own research expertise, not to a research proposal.

Keywords

List keywords that best describe your areas of research expertise. Separate keywords with a semicolon.

Old English; computing in the humanities; textual scholarship; editorial theory; history of the book; reception theory; germanic philology; manuscript studies

Disciplines

Indicate and rank up to 5 disciplines that best correspond to your research interests. Duplicate entries are not permitted.

Rank	Code	Discipline	If Other, specify
1	53008	Mediaeval Literature	
2	53006	Mediaeval Languages	
3	52100	Literature, English	
4	99999	Other	Computers and the Humanities
5	52102	Literature, English - Bibliographical Studies	

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell, Daniel

Funded Research

List up to 8 grants or contracts you have received from SSHRC or other sources. List them in reverse chronological order, based on the year awarded. If you are not the applicant (principal investigator), specify that persons' name.

Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
1	University of Lethbridge, Teaching Development Fund	2003	\$4,500
Role	Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete
Project title	Poetry: A Cultural and Linguistic History		
Applicant's family name	Applicant's given name	Initials	
Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
1	University of Lethbridge, Research Enhancement Award	2002	\$3,000
Role	Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete
Project title	The Anglo-Saxon Reader: A preliminary study		
Applicant's family name	Applicant's given name	Initials	
Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
3010325	Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	2001	\$2,900
Role	Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete
Project title	Student Research Stipend		
Applicant's family name	Applicant's given name	Initials	
Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
3010325	Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	2000	\$4,500
Role	Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete
Project title	SSHRC Special One Time Research Grant [Student Assistance]		
Applicant's family name	Applicant's given name	Initials	

Personal information will be stored in the Personal Information Bank for the appropriate program.

Web CV

Family name, Given name

O'Donnell, Daniel

Funded Research (cont'd)

Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
1	SCP Research Assistant Funding	1999	\$3,600
Role Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete	
Project title Student Research Wage supplement			
Applicant's family name		Applicant's given name	
		Initials	
Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
1	University of Lethbridge Research Fund	1997	\$4,500
Role Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete	
Project title Cædmon's Hymn			
Applicant's family name		Applicant's given name	
		Initials	
Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
1	Research Excellence Envelope (Alberta)	1997	\$4,800
Role Applicant		Completion status <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Complete	
Project title Electronic editing			
Applicant's family name		Applicant's given name	
		Initials	
Org. code	Full name of funding organization	Year awarded (yyyy)	Total amount (CAN\$)
Role		Completion status <input type="checkbox"/> Complete	
Project title			
Applicant's family name		Applicant's given name	
		Initials	

Research Contributions over the Last Six Years (1998-2004)

1. Refereed Contributions: Books, Monographs, Book Chapters, Articles

- R "The Doomsday Machine, or, 'If you build it, will they still come ten years from now?': What Medievalists working in digital media can do to ensure the longevity of their research." *Heroic Age* 7 (2004) <<http://www.mun.ca/mst/heroicage/issues/7/odonnell.html>>.
- R "Numeric and Geometric Patterning in *Cædmon's Hymn*." *ANQ* 17 (2004). 3-12.
- R "'Pioneers! O Pioneers!': Lessons in Electronic Editing from Stijn Streuvels's *De teleurgang van den Waterhoek*." *Literary and Linguistic Computing* 17 ([2003 for] 2002), 491-496.
- R "Junius's Knowledge of the Old English Poem *Durham*." *Anglo-Saxon England* 30 (2002). 231-245.
- R "The Accuracy of the St. Petersburg Bede." *Notes and Queries* 247 (2002): 4-6.
- R "Fish and Fowl: Generic Expectations and the Relationship between the Old English *Phoenix* poem and Lactantius's *de ave phoenice*." In: *Germanic Texts and Latin Models: Medieval Reconstructions*. Ed. K.E. Olsen, A. Harbus and T. Hofstra. *Germania Latina IV. Mediaevalia Groningana*, n.s. 2. Leuven, Paris and Sterling, VA: Peeters, 2001. 157- 71.
- R "*Hædre* and *Hædre Gehogode* (*Solomon and Saturn* line 62b and *Resignation* line 63a)." *Notes and Queries* 244 (1999). 312-316.
- R "The Spirit and the Letter: Literary Embellishment in Old Frisian Legal Texts." *ABzäG* 49 (1998): 245-256.

2. Other Refereed Contributions

- R The Digital Medievalist Project: An Extensible Community of Practice for Medievalists." [Poster and Abstract]. Digital Resources in the Humanities Conference. University of Newcastle upon Tyne, UK. September 5-9, 2004. **Won third prize in poster competition.**
- R "Poetry, Prose, and Book History: A way forward in debates about scribal literacy in Anglo-Saxon England?" 39th International Congress on Medieval Studies, Kalamazoo. May 8, 2003.
- R "Texts and the Single Scholar: Is the morning after worth the night before?" [Lecture on electronic project development and management]. Thirty-eighth International Congress on Medieval Studies (Kalamazoo). May 8, 2003.
- R "'Is that your final answer?'" Reconstructing *Cædmon's Hymn* in a Post-Modern Age." Germanic Philology Session, MLA Annual Meeting. Washington D.C., December 27, 2000.
- R "The Editor Function, or I Know More about *Cædmon's Hymn* than you do, Nyah, Nyah!" Inaugural Lecture, Humanities Computing Series, University of Calgary, June 15, 2000.
- R "Reading Bede Reading *Cædmon*: Understanding a Critical Miracle." Thirty-fifth International Congress on Medieval Studies (Kalamazoo). May 8, 2000.
- R "Reading Bede Reading *Cædmon*: Bede's *Historia ecclesiastica* as Source and Source of Interpretation for *Cædmon's Hymn*." Invited Lecture. Department of English, Queen's University. April 10, 2000.
- R "The Editor Function: Form, Content, and Editorial Theory in Editing *Cædmon's Hymn*." Commissioned Lecture. Thirty-fourth International Congress on Medieval Studies (Kalamazoo). May 9, 1999.
- R "Fish and Fowl: Generic Expectations and the Relationship between the Old English *Phoenix* poem and Lactantius's *de ave phoenice*." *Germania Latina IV*. Groningen, The Netherlands, July 1998.

3. Non-Refereed Contributions

Contributions to SSHRC ITST Workshops

- "Now What? The Digital Medievalist Project and the Discovery of Best Practice." Invited lecture. University of Calgary ITST Summer Institute. May 26, 2004.
- "The Electronic *Cædmon's Hymn*: A Single Scholar, Multiple Text, Electronic Edition and Archive." Invited Lecture. University of Saskatchewan ITST Workshop. May 15th, 2004.
- "The Text Encoding Initiative. A *Theoretical* Standard for the Encoding of Electronic Texts." Invited Lecture. University of Saskatchewan ITST Workshop. May 15th, 2004.

Web Page

“The Electronic *Cædmon’s Hymn*, Editorial Method.” [Web Page]. © 1998.

<<http://people.uleth.ca/~daniel.odonnell/research/caedmon-job.html>>. *This page has been cited a number of times in refereed discussions of digital editing theory.*

Journalism

“More research money needed for Social Sciences and Humanities.” [Radio Broadcast] *Commentary*. CBC Radio 1. Broadcast March 15, 2004.

<<http://www.cbc.ca/insite/COMMENTARY/2004/3/15.html>>

“Restoring Pages to a Sacred Text [The Diary of Anne Frank].” *The Globe and Mail*. Tuesday November 17, 1998. Arts and Leisure, pp. A17-A18.

My teaching on media was the focus of a *Lethbridge Herald* story on media/military relations in Gulf War. “Iraq War More Balanced than 1991: Prof.” *Lethbridge Herald*, April 3, 2003.

Reviews

Donald Scragg and Carole Weinberg, eds. *Literary Appropriations of the Anglo-Saxons from the Thirteenth to the Twentieth Centuries* (Cambridge Studies in Anglo-Saxon England, 29). *Early Medieval Europe* 11 (2002): 184-185.

Timothy Graham, ed. *The Recovery of Old English: Anglo-Saxon Studies in the Sixteenth and Seventeenth Centuries* (Publications of the Richard Rawlinson Center). *Early Medieval Europe* 11 (2002): 93-95.

Hal Momma, *The Composition of Old English Poetry* (Cambridge Studies in Anglo-Saxon England, 20). *Early Medieval Europe* 8 (1999): 163-166.

Lectures

“Vade retro me Satana”: What the Norton Anthology of Poetry gets Wrong on Page 1.” Department of English Colloquium series. University of Lethbridge. November 28, 2002.

“The Cædmon Code: Some Problems with Numerical and Geometrical Patterning in an Early Medieval Text.” Working Papers in the Humanities Colloquium. University of Lethbridge. April 4, 2002.

“Is that your final answer?” Reconstructing *Cædmon’s Hymn* in a Post-Modern Age.” Department of English Research Colloquium, January, 2001.

“Text and Context: Generic Factors affecting Scribal Performance in the Transmission of Old English Verse.” Department of English Research Colloquium. University of Lethbridge. November 15, 2000.

“The Editor Function: Form, Content, and Editorial Theory in Editing *Cædmon’s Hymn*.” Department of English Research Colloquium. University of Lethbridge. February 2, 2000.

“Reading Bede Reading Cædmon: Bede’s *Historia ecclesiastica* as Source and Source of Interpretation for *Cædmon’s Hymn*.” Department of English Research Colloquium. University of Lethbridge. March 1999.

“What Anne Meant: Generic Instability and the Transmission of Anne Frank’s *Diary*.” Department of English Research Colloquium. University of Lethbridge. March 1998.

Reviews of my work

A review of my PhD thesis, “Manuscript Variation in Multiple-Recension Old English Poetic Texts: The Technical Problem and Poetical Art” (1996), was published in *Linguistica e Filologia* 9 (1999): 156.

4. Forthcoming Contributions.

Refereed Contributions: Books, Monographs, Chapters, Articles

R *The Electronic Cædmon’s Hymn*. Society for Early English and Norse Electronic Texts. **Accepted Provisionally** for publication by SEENET (May 2003) for publication by Medieval Academy of America/Boydell and Brewer (Approx 300 pages editorial content). May 2004.

R “Bede’s Strategy in Paraphrasing *Cædmon’s Hymn*.” *JEGP* (**Accepted and at press** for publication in 2004 [submitted 2/2003, accepted 6/2003]).

Other Research Contributions

Consulting and Creative Works

Kawoosh! Productions/Stargate SG-1 [Television Producers]. Advice on historical language use and pronunciation for a Fall 1999 episode of the Television Series “Stargate SG1” (April-May 1999).

Undergraduate and General Interest Lectures

“The Importance of Being Earnest: Coding Problems and Solutions.” Invited Guest Lecture, English 517/607 (Graduate Humanities Computing), University of Calgary. June 15, 2000.

“Tolkien’s Elvish and Other Constructed Languages.” Invited Lecture, English 3700 (Children’s Literature), University of Lethbridge. February 7, 2000.

“Anne, Otto, and the Neo-Nazis. The (Im)morality of Reading a Holocaust Diary.” Invited Lecture, Arts and Science 1000 (Liberal Arts), University of Lethbridge. November 2001; September 2000; November, 1999.

“What Anne Meant: Generic Instability and the Transmission of Anne Frank’s *Diary*.” Invited Lecture, Arts and Science 1000 (Liberal Arts), University of Lethbridge. November 2001; September 2000; November, 1999.

“*Beowulf* and its Place in History.” Worker’s Educational Association Weekend School at Horncastle. February, 1997.

Most Significant Career Research Contributions

R *The Electronic Cædmon’s Hymn*. Society for Early English and Norse Electronic Texts. **Accepted Provisionally** for publication by SEENET (May 2003) for publication by Medieval Academy of America/Boydell and Brewer (Approx 300 pages editorial content). May 2005. ***This work contains the first comprehensive study of Cædmon’s Hymn in its textual and cultural contexts in over 30 years, and the first critical edition of the poem and its manuscript tradition in over 60.***

R “Bede’s Strategy in Paraphrasing Cædmon’s Hymn.” *JEGP* (Accepted and at press for publication in 2004 [submitted 2/2003, accepted 6/2003]). ***Article was praised by a referee as “the most comprehensive treatment and... most balanced discussion these issues that I have seen... Congratulations to the author on producing such a fine study, and to JEGP for getting hold of it!”***

R “Junius’s Knowledge of the Old English Poem *Durham*.” *Anglo-Saxon England* 30 (2002). 231-245. ***Published in the major journal for Anglo-Saxonists, this paper demonstrates that a key version of the Old English poem Durham was a seventeenth-century creation.***

R “A Northumbrian Version of ‘Cædmon’s Hymn’ (*eordu*-recension) in Brussels Bibliothèque Royale Manuscript 8245-57 ff.62r²-v¹: Identification, Edition, and Filiation.” In: *Beda Venerabilis: Historian, Monk and Northumbrian*. Edited by L.A.R.J. Houwen and A.A. MacDonald. Groningen: Egbert Forsten, 1996. 139-166. ***This article announced the identification of a new text of Cædmon’s Hymn. The research in this study was the subject of a significant article by Paul Cavill in Anglia in 2000.***

R “The Collective Sense of Concrete Singular Nouns in *Beowulf*: Emendations of Sense.” *Neuphilologische Mitteilungen* 92 (1991). 433-440. ***I wrote this article as a third year undergraduate: it solves an important crux in Beowulf and has been cited a number of times, including by Alfred Bammesberger.***

Contributions to Training

The University of Lethbridge is a primarily undergraduate institution. Opportunities for graduate instruction are correspondingly limited. Since coming to Lethbridge, I have directed a number of Senior theses and directed reading projects in Book History. I was also a member of the Supervisory Committee for our recently graduated M.A. student, Laura Cappello (M.A. awarded, May, 2003).

Image, Text, Sound and Technology

Les textes, les documents visuels, le son et la technologie

Applicant/Candidat(e):	Dr. Daniel P. O'Donnell
Address/Adresse:	Department of English The University of Lethbridge
File/Dossier:	849-2003-0003
CID:	57402
Title/Titre:	The digital medievalist: an extensible community of practice for image, text, sound and technology research

Committee comments/Commentaires du comité

The committee thought that the research topic was an interesting one and that the participants were well qualified. However, it considered that there were several important factors in the proposal which required substantial improvement.

The committee judged that there was no clear explanation regarding the networking of the Participants or how anticipated networking fitted with the objectives of the ITST program. Moreover, it judged that the budget was not justified in terms of the networking activities of the participants but rather in terms of administrative, technical and conference costs.

In view of its reservations the committee recommended that no award be made.

Out of 28 proposals reviewed by the committee, Council awarded 16 grants in this competition.

Sur un total de 28 demandes soumises au comité, le Conseil a retenu 16 demandes pour l'octroi d'une subvention.

Program Officer/ Agent de programme

Garry Pinard: Tel.: (613) 992-5129
E-Mail/courriel: garry.pinard@sshrc.ca

RE: ITST Digital Medievalist Project Proposal
September 13, 2004

The proposal by the Digital Medievalist Project group is an excellent fit with SSHRC's ITST Networking grant. Its objectives reflect those stated in the ITST description: integration of digital technologies into the humanities and social sciences; bringing together researchers and graduate students whose work involves merging digital technologies with humanities investigation; facilitating national and, in this case, international, networks of researchers doing this type of work. The Digital Medievalist Project proposal is well timed: the extensive and extremely well qualified group of researchers is poised to make excellent and efficient use of the grant, and O'Donnell understands the digital editing area, the people in it, and what yet needs to be accomplished, better than anyone in the country. The networked collaboration as is proposed here will therefore yield precisely the results SSHRC is looking for with its ITST program.

Medieval texts, the evidential basis of the proposed project, are among the best suited of all literary texts for digitized data entry, editing and archiving. Their complex histories and multiple translations have proved to be barriers to understanding them via hardcopy transmission: the necessary information to be included is too vast, and too continually in need of updating, to be accommodated by the paper page. The network O'Donnell has already begun, and is proposing to increase and intensify with the ITST grant, is the next logical, and necessary, step in rendering these most important literary texts understandable and accessible to researchers, students and general readers.

To put it another way, Canada can become a leader in this kind of work through a network such as this one, and will surely be overtaken by researchers in Britain, France or the United States if this kind of proposal remains unfunded here. The work that the group will undertake is timely and ready to be done, and the literary community has reached the point where the next digital steps, represented in this proposal, are recognized to be necessary and inevitable. This proposal, it seems clear to me, is aware of this; its collaborators are fully qualified, and excellently prepared, to undertake the work, and SSHRC's ITST network grant is perfectly timed and organized to allow them to do it.

Professor

The University of Virginia
Charlottesville, VA 22904-4121

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September 10, 2004

The Adjudication Committee
 Image, Text, Sound and Technology Program
 Strategic Programs and Joint Initiative Division
 Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council

Professor Daniel O'Donnell has assembled a distinguished group of young medievalists who are using electronic technology to examine early medieval Britain literature, art, and history. Their goal, already partially realized, was to establish a formalized communications forum for the exchange of ideas and information to establish "best practices" for researchers using electronic technology. The need for such a forum is urgent, as scholars across the world are currently working independently and usually in ignorance of other scholars working the same vein, all inventing and re-inventing very similar wheels. The duplication of effort is staggeringly inefficient. All three segments of The Digital Medievalist will make communication very much easier for those of us engaged in creating electronic projects both large and small.

I predicted about this time last year that The Digital Medievalist discussions and papers would provide individual project directors with a better basis for working with librarians in the digitization of images. At present, the major libraries in this country and Europe all have different policies and practices for creating color digital images. A "best practice" consensus on imaging standards established by the project can materially assist scholars in dealing with photographic duplication sections of research libraries. Progress is beginning to be made.

The Digital Medievalist mailing list is already very active, full of useful insight and information on various aspects of the technology, serving to introduce me, at least, to a number of the players in this diverse field. The about-to-be-launched web site, which I have only briefly looked at in a beta form, promises to be extraordinarily useful.

The scholars directing The Digital Medievalist are among the most knowledgeable and competent medievalists presently engaged in electronic scholarship. They and their project are very much worthy of your support.

Professor and Director, Society for Early
 English Electronic Texts (*SEENET*)
 Project Director, *The Piers Plowman*
 Electronic Archive

and Sage

Old English Newsletter
Department of English
The University of Tennessee
Knoxville TN 37996-0430
10 September 2004

Adjudication Committee
Image, Text, Sound and Technology Program
Strategic Programs and Joint Initiatives Division
Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council
350 Albert Street
P.O. Box 1610
Ottawa, ON K1P 6G4, CANADA

To the Members of the Committee:

As a scholar interested in the intersections of textual scholarship and technology, I enthusiastically endorse Professor O'Donnell's "Digital Medievalist" initiative; in my role as editor of the *Old English Newsletter*, I am happy to endorse it officially as well. The journal's endorsement is appropriate for two reasons. *OEN* has long relied on the generous collaboration and expertise of a large body of contributors, reviewers, editors and advisors, which makes it a good example of the benefits of the "Community of Practice" model described in Professor O'Donnell's proposal. Moreover, because we plan to place some of the journal's content online in the near future, we expect to benefit directly from the gathering of information and technical skill created by this initiative.

As the proposal notes, Anglo-Saxon studies has a long history of successful collaborative projects, among them the *Dictionary of Old English*, the *Fontes Anglo-Saxonici* database, and the recently-completed *Sancta Crux/Halig Rod* project, a three-year series of symposia on the role of the Cross in Anglo-Saxon culture. The idea of a collaborative project for digital editing will be entirely congruent with these other large-scale multi-disciplinary enterprises; for many scholars in the Medieval Studies, the habits of working together will be familiar ones. In many respects, however, it is unlike these other projects in interesting and appealing ways: while the principle behind some large undertakings is to collect the scholarship of many people and publish it as one work (usually under the name of one or two General Editors), the principle behind the "Digital Medievalist" initiative is to collect not scholarship but techniques, and offer them freely to individuals or groups who can use it in their own work. Rather than distributing the work and centralizing the information, one might say, this project centralizes the work and distributes the information.

Medievalists have also been quick to recognize the benefits of new technologies, from early discussion lists to recent online databases; perhaps it has something to do with the fact that we have always had to solve the problems associated with reproducing the non-standard letters and figures in the texts we study—from hunting for Icelandic 'golf-ball' elements for IBM Selectric typewriters to learning the intricacies of Unicode, we are accustomed to stretching the limits of available technology in our everyday work. This necessary familiarity has paid off handsomely in recent projects like Kevin Kiernan's *Electronic Beowulf*, Martin Foy's *Bayeux Tapestry* edition and the recently published *Dictionary of Old English, A-F*, all on CD-ROM. These are exemplary productions in many respects—certainly they have expanded our notion of what is possible in the area

of electronic publishing. But they are unfortunately not typical of the level of professionalism and creativity in electronic projects. Professor O'Donnell's proposal addresses, and I think will rectify, the central problem of such works: the difficulty of learning the technology required to create them often slows down or places limits on the scholarship they are meant to display. By providing a venue for sharing information and a clearinghouse for technical advice, this project will make the job of any aspiring editor much easier. It will also help create the kind of consistency that is much needed in projects of this sort, if they are going to have any more value than a printed book.

When I was editing the Old English version of the Gospels, I found myself wishing time and again for a guide to the practice of editing—not the theory (there is no shortage of works on the *theory* of editing), but the pragmatic nuts-and-bolts details of the task before me. Straight answers even to simple questions (which abbreviations should be used in a glossary? how are textual variants signaled in the text? what kinds of annotations are considered universally necessary?) were surprisingly hard to find; I taught myself by imitating other editions, and by seeking advice from scholars who had edited similarly complex texts. I suspect this is how it has always been done—editing is something of a craft, learned by imitation, apprenticeship, and the production of journeyman efforts (I was fortunate to have the expert guidance of a professional publisher and typesetter, who imposed consistency on my uneven work and made it conform to the 'house style' of the series in which it appeared). Scholars working on electronic editions and reference works are in an even worse position—they face the same dearth of practical guidance that I did, but they also must deal with a bewildering complexity of technological issues in a still-evolving set of coding languages (HTML, JavaScript, XML, etc.) across several operating platforms, and an almost total absence of agreement on what, exactly, a digital edition is supposed to look like. Every editor ends up to some extent re-inventing basic ways to present his or her information; this presentation must be both comprehensible to the user of a traditional edition and useful to anyone who might want to re-use the work in unplanned ways. It is hard enough to edit a text; to add the complexity of electronic publication and the imagining of the unforeseen future increases the difficulty by several orders of magnitude.

Professor O'Donnell has already achieved some success in this project; the Digital Medievalist has sponsored well-attended sessions at the International Congress on Medieval Studies at Kalamazoo in 2004, and has more sessions planned for 2005. It has given rise to a lively and exceptionally informed internet discussion list, DM-L, where scholars from many fields and periods of study can ask questions, share information, and collaborate informally to improve the quality of their individual scholarship. I know of no other such resource in the field today. There are few venues in which researchers from the international scholarly world, with diverse interests and common goals or with common interests and diverse goals, can share their expertise and increase their knowledge at the same time; scholarly conferences are generally arranged to favor the presentation of completed works rather than tentative explorations, and seminars or fellowships tend to encourage individual rather than collaborative inquiry. The real importance of O'Donnell's project lies in the opportunities it offers, and has already offered, for new forms of professional interaction among scholars of the Middle Ages. By focusing on new methods of digital presentation of source material, the Digital Medievalist initiative answers a critical need for the translation of traditional expertise in textual editing and codicology to the new electronic media which will shape the future of all scholarship. Both virtually and in person, this project is already achieving impressive success in creating a community of scholars dedicated to this fundamentally important task.

As electronic resources become more commonplace, I believe the creation of a "Community of Practice" will be a useful, even necessary, step towards making such publications more respected,

more rigorous, more widespread, and more important. Professor O'Donnell's proposal is timely, well-conceived, reasonable in its expectations, accurate in its assessment of the current state of affairs, and both creative and efficient in its proposal of solutions to the problems it addresses; I endorse it without reservation. I am sure it will make a substantial difference in the quality of work produced as well as in the amount of effort required to produce it. The sharing of information, review of projects and reports, and archiving of resources will make it easier to do better work, something that will benefit not only editors but their readers as well. I look forward to the outcome of this initiative; any support given to it will have long-lasting benefits for a large body of scholars, students, and general readers.

Roy M. Liuzza
Professor of English, University of Tennessee
Editor, *Old English Newsletter*